

The Effect of Archives Management on Work Efficiency of Land Office Staffs in Land Certification Services in Timor - Leste

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Abstract:- Archives have important value and role because archives are the official evidence regarding the administration of government and also the evidence of the people's life in Timor-Leste. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of filing management on work efficiency of the land office staffs in providing land titling services in Timor-Leste.

This type of research is quantitative. The object of research is archive management and work efficiency. The number of samples used was 69 respondents using the total sampling method. Collecting the data by using Likert scale questionnaire. The data analysis technique used was the simple linear regression test. Hypothesis testing was carried out by using the T Test. The results of the study show that archive management has a positive and significant effect on the work efficiency of the Land Office Staffs in providing land certification services in Timor-Leste.

Keywords: Archives, Work Efficiency, Timor-Leste Land Office.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's modern information era, the need to fulfill job satisfaction has increased with the intense competition within the scope of companies and agencies. Therefore, there are many demands, one of which is the totality in carrying out the fulfillment of the goals of the agency. One thing that is often overlooked by the majority of agencies is the archival activities. There are still many agencies that pay little attention to the condition of archives that actually have important meaning for these agencies. Every work and office activity, both government and private requires storage, recording that can be accounted for (Julianto, 2018).

The filing system itself basically consists of storage according to alphabetical order, storage according to subject, storage according to area, storage according to number and storage according to date. In order for archives to provide maximum information, it is necessary to manage records properly and regularly, so that they will assist leaders in planning and making decisions. Archive management in the office must be improved to support the increase. Besides that, it can also save time, thought, effort and cost.

Thus the management of archives in the office must be improved to support the improvement and work efficiency of employees (Sambas, 2016). Work efficiency is one of the organizational principles in carrying out a job according to applicable procedures, with minimum effort but achieving maximum results in accordance with the goals set.

Every government organization/agency needs to implement work efficiency in carrying out its duties. Work efficiency really supports the success of government organizations/agencies in providing services to the community and serving the country (Priansa, 2018). The Timor-Leste Land Office is a vertical agency of the Agrarian Directorate under the office of the Ministry of Public Works under the auspices of the Ministry of Public Labor of the Democratic Republic of Timor-Leste. The task of the Timor-Leste Land Office is to carry out the main duties of the Agrarian Directorate in state revenue. In 2003 the government established the implementation of surveys, measurements and mapping, implementation of determination of land rights, land registration and community empowerment.

In carrying out their respective duties in each field at the Timor-Leste Land Office, they will always deal with more and more archives every day. Records management needs to be done properly and maximally to make it easier for employees to carry out their duties so as to achieve work efficiency. It seems that the management of the archives

carried out at the Timor-Leste Land Office is still not well organized, one of which is the problem with the large number of irregular files in the filing cabinet which can affect the work efficiency of employees. This can happen because there are problems related to archive management and work efficiency, for example there are still archives that have not been organized properly because employees pay less attention to the arrangement of the archives, lack of archive storage so that the archives to be stored are not organized according to the storage system.

Some employees are not careful in storing archives so that the archives they are looking for are not found, causing every work to be hampered. Therefore, the management of archives in the office can greatly affect the work efficiency of employees because with good archive management, employee work efficiency will increase and organizational

goals can be achieved in accordance with the goals of the Timor-Leste Land Office.

Based on the things that have been stated above, the writer is interested in raising the title "The Influence of Archives Management on Employee Work Efficiency at the Land Office in Land Certification Services in Timor-Leste". Based on this background, the formulation of the research problem is how does archive management affect the work efficiency of employees at the Land Office in providing land certification services in Timor-Leste.

Based on the theory described earlier and the results of previous research, the variables used in this research are filing management and work efficiency. So that research framework can be described as in Figure 1 :

Fig 1 The Framework for Thinking about the Influence of Archives Management on Work Efficiency

From the description above, it can be put forward the hypothesis in this research, there are:

H1 : Archive management has a positive and significant effect on the work efficiency of employees at the Land Office in Land Certification Services in Timor-Leste.

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of filing management on the work efficiency of employees at the Land Office in providing land titling services in Timor-Leste. The use of this research is expected to add

insight and reference for readers regarding the influence of archives management on the work efficiency of employees at the land office in land certification services in Timor Leste. This research can also be used as a reference and reference material for further research. It is hoped that this research can also be used as a reference for institutions in improving land titling services in Timor-Leste.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The object of this research is the influence of archive management on employee work efficiency. The research subjects are employees of the Land Office in the Service of Land Certification in Timor-Leste. The variables used in this study are clearly defined with indicators that accompany of them, so that they do not create misunderstandings for respondents when collecting data. The author uses two variables, namely the independent/ independent variable and the dependent/ dependent variable. The data analysis technique used was descriptive qualitative, namely explaining the results of the questionnaire tabulation, and quantitative by using a statistical test tool, namely linear regression with SPSS Tools.

III. FINDING AND DISCUSSIONS

From the information processing, the consequences display that there is a effective and great influence of submitting control (X) on the paintings performance (Y) of employees at the Timor-Leste Land workplace. primarily based at the records that has been accumulated and the

assessments that have been completed on the hassle with the simple regression version, the consequences of the analysis and discussion which have been accomplished on this observe, it could be concluded that files control (X) has a significance value of zero.000, which means that that files management has a fantastic impact and big effect at the work efficiency of Timor-Leste Land workplace employees. this is the realization of this research. based on the effects of research that has been performed regarding the impact of archive management on paintings performance, the subsequent suggestion may be given: it is miles hoped that the Timor-Leste Land workplace will take note of the archive management gadget currently in use, in order that it's miles more bendy to changing times, because the future documents will not best be in physical form, but also, of path, in the virtual form.

A. A Simple Regression Analysis

The simple linear analysis is used to investigate the impact of data management on work performance. The effects of the evaluation acquired can be visible in the following of Table 1:

Table 1 Simple Linear Regression Results

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,325	,954		,340	,735
	X	,838	,037	,940	22,563	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on a, b1 values, the equation of the linear regression line between archive management and work efficiency is: $Y = 0,325 + 0,838X$ provide that information:

- In the linear regression equation, a constant value of 0.325 means that if the independent variable for filing management (X) is equal to zero, then the value of work efficiency is 0.325.
- The work efficiency coefficient (X) of 0.838 means an increase in the management of one unit of records, so the value of work efficiency has increased by 0.838.

B. Hypothesis Test Results

► T-test Result

The consequences of the t-test have been accomplished on this examine to decide the importance of the impact of the independent variables, there are: archive management (X) to the dependent variable of work efficiency (Y). The test results (T-test) can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2 T-test Result

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,325	,954		,340	,735
	X	,838	,037	,940	22,563	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

From Table 2 above, the result of T-test can be explained, there is:

- The significance value of archive management is 0.000, less than 0.05.

This means that archive management has a positive and significant effect on work efficiency. This shows the hypothesis is accepted.

C. The Influence of Records Management (X) on Work Efficiency (Y)

Based on the results of the study, archive management (X) has a positive and significant effect on work efficiency (Y) at the Timor-Leste Land Office, which can be analyzed through the regression coefficient (b).

Regression coefficient of b_1X_1 is 0,838 it means that every increase in filing management (X) can increase work efficiency (Y). So it can be concluded that archive management has a positive and significant influence on employee work efficiency. This is confirmed in testing the hypothesis with the formula $H_0 =$ there is no positive effect of archives management (X) on employee work efficiency (Y), and $H_a =$ there is a positive and significant effect between archives management (X) and work efficiency (Y) showing the results that the regression coefficient b_1X_1 : calculated = 22,5639 > t tabel (0,05: 67) = 1,6 dan Sig. t = 0,000 ($p < 0,05$). This shows that H_0 rejected and accepts H_1 , and has a significant effect. This means that there is a positive and significant influence of filing management (X) on the work efficiency (Y) of employees at the Timor-Leste Land Office.

Archive management carried out in an office is basically very influential on employee work efficiency. Archives that are organized and well organized will make it easier for employees to find archives again in a short time. So employees do not have to linger to find the archives they need. By implementing good archive management, it means being able to organize, compile, and collect programmed records or documents and be able to destroy them in the most appropriate way. Organizing archives is one of the aspects that must be applied in achieving office goals to support increased productivity and efficiency of office work. Thus the employee's work will run more smoothly, so that coordination and supervision will be easier. Because it is impossible for the leadership to take care of the archives themselves, thus the leadership expects its staff to be truly capable of managing and maintaining records for the leadership and for the benefit of the organization as a whole. Thus it can be said that archive management is the first step that needs to be addressed to improve work efficiency (Sedarmayanti, 2003).

The results of the research are in line with Khasanah, U. (2018), Kajual (2017) and Julianto (2018) which states that archival management has a positive and significant effect on employee work efficiency.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based totally at the facts that has been amassed and the assessments which have been achieved on the hassle with the easy regression model, the results of the analysis and dialogue which have been done on this look at, it is able to be concluded that (X) has a significance value of 0.000, which means that archives management has a positive effect and significant impact on the work efficiency of the Timor-Leste Land Office staff.

Additionally, results of the research that has been done regarding the effect of archives management on work efficiency, the following suggestions can be given:

It is hoped that the Timor-Leste Land Office will pay attention to the archive management system currently in use, so that it is more flexible to changing times, because future archives will not only be in physical form but digital in nature.

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